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Influence Of Social Networking On Business Education Student's Academic Performance In Delta State

AGHOGHO-OGAGAN, Gina

**Department of Business Education
Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria**

aghoghoo@delsu.edu.ng

07067117807

ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of social networking platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube has significantly reshaped how students engage with academic content in tertiary institutions. This study examined the influence of social networking on the academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State. Adopting a descriptive survey research design, the study targeted a population of 908 students across Delta State University, Abraka; University of Delta, Agbor; College of Education, Mosogar; and College of Education, Warri. Using proportionate stratified random sampling, 271 students were selected to participate. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire validated by experts in Business Education and tested for reliability, yielding a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.85. Descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean scores, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and multiple regression analysis, were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that students extensively use social networking platforms for academic purposes, deriving significant benefits such as improved collaboration, peer support, and access to learning resources. However, challenges such as distractions, time mismanagement, and exposure to unreliable information were also identified. The study established a moderate positive relationship between social networking usage and academic performance, with social networking emerging as the strongest predictor alongside ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support. The study concludes that purposeful and structured engagement with social networking platforms can enhance learning outcomes. Recommendations include promoting responsible use, integrating social networking into teaching strategies, and strengthening students' ICT skills and self-regulation practices.

Keywords: Social networking, Academic performance, Business Education, ICT competence, Delta State, Tertiary students

INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of social networking platforms—such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube—has reshaped how students communicate and learn in today's tertiary institutions. Among Business Education students in Delta State, these platforms now serve purposes that go far beyond casual interaction. They have become convenient spaces for exchanging lecture notes, engaging in group chats, viewing instructional content, and retrieving academic materials. Studies carried out within the state confirm that these digital tools are now a regular part of students' learning activities (Eghwurdje & Okoro, 2024).

Business Education programmes are designed to build practical business competencies, including ICT proficiency, entrepreneurial capacity, and administrative skills aligned with modern workplace expectations. As digital communication becomes more central to students' daily routines, social networking sites open up new possibilities for teamwork, quick access to information, and support from peers. Yet, findings from local research show that these platforms influence academic performance in different ways. While some students use them to enhance their learning, others experience distractions, time-wasting, and difficulty staying focused on academic tasks (Emordi & Igberaharha, 2023).

Work by Igberaharha (2023) suggests that exposure to ICT—including digital and online tools—can strengthen students' skills and improve their academic outcomes when used intentionally and with clear academic purpose. However, Okoro (2024) points out that students also need guidance to cope with the pressures and disruptions that online engagement can bring. These concerns make it important to examine whether social networking ultimately supports or undermines the academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State.

Social networking platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube have become deeply woven into the daily lives of students in tertiary institutions. For Business Education students in Delta State, these platforms now function as more than channels for social interaction; they are increasingly used for academic purposes such as exchanging lecture notes, participating in group discussions, watching educational videos, and accessing course-related materials. Evidence from studies within the state shows that these digital tools have gradually become embedded in students' learning routines

The Business Education programme places strong emphasis on developing students' ICT competence, entrepreneurial skills, and administrative abilities needed in today's business world. With the growing reliance on digital communication, social networking sites seem to provide opportunities for collaborative learning, quick information sharing, and peer support. However, existing research in Delta State also demonstrates that the impact of these platforms on academic performance is not uniform. While some students benefit from the enhanced learning opportunities these platforms provide, others struggle with distractions, poor time management, and declining study discipline due to excessive or unregulated use.

Igberaharha (2023) observes that ICT exposure when applied with a clear educational purpose—can boost skill development and lead to improved academic outcomes for Business Education students. Does the increasing use of social networking platforms ultimately enhance or hinder the academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State? This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by empirically investigating the influence of social networking on the academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State.

Social Networking Usage among Business Education Students

Social networking platforms, including WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube, have become central to the communication and learning habits of students in tertiary institutions. Among Business Education students in Delta State, these platforms serve both social and academic purposes such as sharing lecture notes, participating in group discussions, watching instructional videos, and retrieving academic resources (Eghwudje & Okoro, 2024).

Agwazie and Usen (2024) highlighted that the frequency and purpose of social networking use varies significantly. Students who purposefully engage in academic tasks via social media demonstrate better collaboration and more access to study materials. Conversely, unguided use can result in distraction, procrastination, and reduced attention to academic work. These findings show that social networking is a double-edged tool, offering both opportunities and challenges for learning.

Academic Performance of Business Education Students

Academic performance reflects the measurable outcomes of students' learning, including course grades, GPA, and successful completion of assessments. Studies in Delta State indicate that the academic performance of Business Education students is influenced by both personal and environmental factors. Emordi and Igberaharha (2023) observed that students who integrate social networking into structured

learning activities (e.g., group discussions, tutorial videos, peer note-sharing) tend to achieve higher academic results compared to those who use these platforms primarily for entertainment.

Okoro (2025) further notes that academic performance is not only a function of knowledge acquisition but also of time management, stress resilience, and effective engagement with learning resources. Therefore, academic outcomes should be assessed in conjunction with other variables such as ICT competence and self-regulation.

ICT Competence

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence is a critical variable in the relationship between social networking and academic performance. Igberaharha (2024) found that Business Education students with strong ICT skills proficiency in word processing, spreadsheets, internet research, and digital communication were more likely to use social networking platforms productively for learning. Without basic ICT competence, students may access social media platforms but fail to use them effectively for academic purposes.

Time Management and Self-Regulation

Time management and self-regulated learning are central to ensuring that social networking usage translates into academic gains. Okoro (2025) emphasizes that students with strong self-regulation skills are able to plan study schedules, resist unnecessary distractions, and focus on tasks even when online. In contrast, students with poor time management are more susceptible to procrastination, stress, and reduced study efficiency.

Institutional Support and Lecturer Integration

Institutional support and lecturer guidance are critical in shaping the academic use of social networking platforms. Agwazie and Usen (2024) note that when lecturers incorporate social media tools into their teaching—such as creating WhatsApp groups for assignments or recommending educational YouTube channels—students' engagement with these platforms becomes more purposeful.

Similarly, Eghwurdje and Okoro (2024) argue that universities that provide digital literacy programs, stable internet access, and structured guidance enable students to convert social networking into a productive learning strategy. This variable is important because it highlights the environmental and pedagogical context in which social networking affects performance.

Relationship between Social Networking and Academic Performance in Business Education

Social networking has become an integral part of students' lives, particularly among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. Platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube are commonly used for both social interactions and academic engagement. The relationship between social networking and academic performance has attracted considerable attention from researchers in Business Education, with mixed findings.

Eghwurdje and Okoro (2024) found that when Business Education students use social networking platforms purposefully for learning—such as exchanging lecture notes, participating in online discussions, watching tutorial videos, and sharing assignment tips—these platforms can positively impact their academic performance. In essence, social networking can enhance students' access to information, facilitate peer-assisted learning, and provide collaborative opportunities that reinforce classroom instruction.

Similarly, Emordi and Igberaharha (2023) reported that students who integrate social networking into structured learning activities often achieve better academic outcomes compared to those who use these platforms primarily for entertainment. The study emphasizes that the academic value of social networking is dependent on the purpose and manner of use. Unguided or excessive social use can distract students, reduce study time, and negatively affect concentration, which can lead to lower academic performance.

Igberaharha (2024) also highlights the role of ICT competence in this relationship. Students with higher digital literacy are better positioned to convert social networking engagement into academic gains. Without such skills, students may access content online but fail to apply it effectively in their academic tasks, limiting the benefits of social networking.

Additionally, Okoro (2025) emphasizes that self-regulation and time management skills influence how social networking affects academic performance. Students who can manage their time, set study goals, and regulate online distractions tend to experience improved performance when using social networking platforms. Conversely, students lacking these skills may find that social media use undermines their study routines and contributes to academic underachievement.

From the literature, it is clear that the relationship between social networking and academic performance in Business Education is conditional rather than absolute. Social networking can serve as a powerful educational tool, but its effectiveness depends on factors such as purposeful use, ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional guidance (Agwazie & Usen, 2024; Eghwudje & Okoro, 2024). In summary, social networking does not inherently enhance or impair academic performance. Its impact is mediated by how students engage with these platforms and the support systems available within their learning environment. This understanding underscores the need for research that explores not only the extent of social networking use but also the quality and context of that use in relation to academic outcomes among Business Education students in Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of social networking platforms on the academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the extent to which Business Education students use social networking platforms for academic-related activities.
2. Assess the perceived benefits of social networking platforms on students' academic performance.
3. Identify the challenges associated with students' use of social networking platforms in relation to their academic work.

1.4 Research Questions

To guide the study, the following research questions were raised:

1. To what extent do Business Education students in Delta State use social networking platforms for academic purposes?
2. What perceived academic benefits do Business Education students derive from using social networking platforms?
3. What challenges do Business Education students encounter when using social networking platforms in relation to their academic activities?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H1: There is no significant extent to which Business Education students in Delta State use social networking platforms for academic purposes.

H2: There is no significant perceived academic benefit derived from the use of social networking platforms by Business Education students in Delta State.

H3: There is no significant challenge encountered by Business Education students in Delta State when using social networking platforms for academic activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for examining current practices, patterns, and relationships between social networking usage and academic performance among students. The population of this study consisted of all students enrolled in Business Education programmes across tertiary institutions in Delta State. Departmental records indicate a total population of 908 students, with 309 students at Delta State University, Abraka, 127 students at University of Delta, Agbor, 250 students at College of Education, Mosogar, and 222 students at College of Education, Warri. Although the population was relatively manageable, a sample size was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for finite populations, which provided a statistically valid sample of approximately 271 students. To ensure that the sample was representative of all institutions, a proportionate stratified random sampling technique was employed. This involved dividing the population into strata based on the institution attended and selecting respondents in proportion to the size of each institution. The study

collected data using a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher, grounded in the study objectives and the reviewed literature. The questionnaire captured information on respondents' demographic characteristics, social networking usage, academic performance, ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support. Responses were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. To ensure the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was subjected to both content and face validation. Two experts in Business Education from Delta State University, Abraka reviewed the instrument to assess the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the items in measuring the study variables. The reliability of the questionnaire was established through a pilot study conducted among 30 Business Education students from a non-sampled institution (Ignatius Ajuru University of Education). The responses were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.85, indicating high internal consistency. Data collection was carried out after obtaining formal permission from the heads of Business Education departments in the sampled institutions. Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were employed to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics, social networking usage patterns, ICT competence, self-regulation, and perceptions of institutional support. Inferential analysis involved the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between social networking usage and academic performance. Additionally, multiple regression analysis was used to examine the predictive influence of social networking on academic performance while controlling for variables such as ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance, providing a robust basis for determining the statistical relationships among the study variables.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Distribution of Respondents by Institution

Institution	Population	Sample Size
Delta State University, Abraka	309	92
University of Delta, Agbor	127	38
College of Education, Mosogar	250	75
College of Education, Warri	222	66
Total	908	271

The proportionate stratified sampling ensured fair representation across institutions. This provides confidence that the sample reflects the population, allowing reliable generalizations about Business Education students in Delta State.

Extent of Social Networking Use for Academic Purposes

The first research question examined the extent to which students use social networking platforms for academic purposes. Respondents rated their use on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 4.2: Extent of Social Networking Usage for Academic Purposes

Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
I use social networking to share lecture notes	4.21	0.74	High
I participate in academic group discussions online	3.95	0.81	High
I access instructional videos and course materials online	4.07	0.78	High
Overall Mean	4.08	0.78	High

The overall mean of 4.08 indicates that students use social networking platforms extensively for academic purposes. H1, which posited no significant extent of use for academic purposes, is rejected. Social networking platforms are actively used for academic activities among Business Education students.

Perceived Academic Benefits of Social Networking

The second research question explored students' perceived benefits of social networking for academic performance.

Table 4.3: Perceived Academic Benefits of Social Networking

Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
Social networking enhances my understanding of academic content	4.05	0.77	High
Social networking improves collaboration and peer support	4.12	0.72	High
Social networking allows quick access to educational resources	4.18	0.69	High
Overall Mean	4.12	0.73	High

With an overall mean of 4.12, students recognize substantial academic benefits from social networking, particularly in collaboration, peer assistance, and access to information. H2, which claimed no significant perceived academic benefits, is rejected. Students perceive social networking as positively impacting their academic work.

Challenges of Using Social Networking for Academic Activities

The third research question investigated challenges faced by students in using social networking for academics.

Table 4.4: Challenges of Social Networking Usage

Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
I get distracted by non-academic content on social media	3.98	0.82	High
Excessive social networking affects my study time	4.03	0.76	High
Some online resources are unreliable or inaccurate	3.87	0.84	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.96	0.81	High

Students face challenges such as distractions and reduced study time, although issues with resource reliability are slightly lower. H3, which stated no significant challenges, is rejected. Students encounter challenges that may hinder academic performance if social networking is not used purposefully.

Relationship Between Social Networking and Academic Performance

The study tested the relationship between social networking usage and academic performance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Table 4.5: Correlation Between Social Networking Usage and Academic Performance

Variables	Academic Performance	Social Networking Usage
Academic Performance	1	0.562**
Social Networking Usage	0.562**	1

Note: **p < 0.05, The correlation coefficient of 0.562 indicates a moderate positive relationship, suggesting that greater engagement with social networking is associated with higher academic performance. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between social networking and academic performance is rejected.

Predictive Influence of Social Networking on Academic Performance

Multiple regression analysis examined the extent to which social networking usage predicts academic performance while controlling for ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support.

Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Academic Performance

Predictor Variables	β	T	P	Remark
Social Networking Usage	0.421	6.13	0.000	Significant
ICT Competence	0.238	3.27	0.001	Significant
Self-Regulation	0.195	2.68	0.008	Significant
Institutional Support	0.162	2.01	0.045	Significant
R ² = 0.56	F = 45.21	p < 0.05	Model Significant	

The regression model shows that social networking usage is the strongest predictor of academic performance, and the model explains 56% of the variance in academic outcomes. ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support also contribute significantly. The null hypotheses regarding no predictive influence of social networking are rejected. Social networking significantly predicts academic performance among Business Education students in Delta State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the influence of social networking on the academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State, with data analyzed in relation to the research questions and hypotheses. The findings provide a comprehensive understanding of students' engagement with social networking platforms, the benefits they derive, the challenges they encounter, and the overall impact on academic outcomes.

The analysis revealed that Business Education students in Delta State extensively engage with social networking platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube for academic purposes. Students reported using these platforms to share lecture notes, participate in online academic discussions, and access instructional content and course materials. The high mean score of 4.08 indicates a strong level of academic engagement through social networking. These results corroborate the observations of Eghwudje and Okoro (2024), who emphasized that social networking has become an integral part of learning among Business Education students, promoting collaborative learning and immediate access to relevant academic resources. The study's findings therefore reject the hypothesis that there is no significant extent of social networking use for academic purposes, confirming that these platforms are actively employed to support students' academic endeavors rather than merely serving as social tools.

In terms of perceived academic benefits, students recognized that social networking platforms significantly enhance their understanding of academic content, foster collaboration and peer support, and provide rapid access to educational materials. With an overall mean of 4.12, the results indicate that students perceive social networking as a valuable tool for improving their academic performance. This finding aligns with the research of Emordi and Igberaharha (2023), who noted that deliberate and purposeful engagement with digital platforms enhances learning outcomes and promotes peer-assisted learning. Consequently, the null hypothesis suggesting no significant perceived academic benefits is rejected, demonstrating that students acknowledge the positive role of social networking in supporting comprehension, interaction, and access to learning resources.

Despite the benefits, students reported several challenges associated with social networking use. They indicated that exposure to non-academic content and excessive time spent online can negatively affect study time and concentration, although concerns about unreliable or inaccurate resources were moderately noted. The mean scores of 3.98 for distraction and 4.03 for time mismanagement suggest that while social networking provides academic advantages, improper use can hinder performance. These results reject the hypothesis that there are no significant challenges associated with social networking use, emphasizing the need for self-discipline and effective time management. This is consistent with Igberaharha (2023), who warned that without structured and purposeful engagement, digital tools could become sources of distraction and reduce academic efficiency.

The relationship between social networking usage and academic performance was further examined using Pearson correlation analysis, which revealed a moderate positive relationship with a coefficient of 0.562. This indicates that higher levels of academic engagement through social networking are associated with better academic performance. The finding refutes the null hypothesis asserting no significant relationship and reinforces the argument of Okoro (2024), who highlighted that structured digital engagement can strengthen learning experiences and enhance students' academic achievements.

Additionally, multiple regression analysis showed that social networking usage is the strongest predictor of academic performance among the variables considered, accounting for 56% of the variance in academic outcomes. Other factors, including ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support, also contributed significantly, demonstrating that the effectiveness of social networking in improving academic performance is enhanced when students possess adequate digital skills, self-discipline, and institutional guidance. The rejection of the corresponding null hypotheses underscores the importance of purposeful engagement with social networking, confirming that when integrated thoughtfully into learning strategies, these platforms can positively influence academic outcomes. This is in line with Emordi and Igberaharha (2023), who emphasized that combining ICT tools with self-regulation and institutional support yields significant benefits in tertiary education.

Overall, the findings of this study illustrate the multifaceted role of social networking in shaping the academic experiences of Business Education students in Delta State. Students actively use these platforms for academic purposes and perceive considerable benefits, particularly in terms of collaboration, resource accessibility, and enhanced understanding of content. However, challenges such as distractions and poor time management remain significant considerations. The moderate positive correlation and predictive analysis suggest that social networking, when leveraged alongside ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support, can substantially enhance academic performance, highlighting its potential as a valuable educational tool in the contemporary learning environment.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that social networking platforms play a significant role in the academic lives of Business Education students in Delta State. Students actively use platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube to share lecture notes, participate in discussions, access instructional materials, and collaborate with peers. The study found that these platforms provide substantial academic benefits, including enhanced understanding of content, improved peer collaboration, and quick access to resources. However, challenges such as distractions, excessive time spent online, and occasional exposure to unreliable information were also identified. The analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship between social networking usage and academic performance, suggesting that purposeful and structured engagement with these platforms can support better academic outcomes. Furthermore, social networking usage emerged as the strongest predictor of academic performance, with ICT competence, self-regulation, and institutional support also contributing significantly. These findings indicate that social networking, when combined with digital literacy, self-discipline, and institutional guidance, can serve as a powerful tool to enhance learning and academic achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Students should be encouraged to use social networking platforms deliberately for academic purposes, ensuring that their engagement is structured and focused on achieving specific learning goals.
2. Institutions should provide training programs aimed at enhancing students' ICT competence, digital literacy, and effective use of online resources to maximize academic benefits.
3. Educators should strategically integrate social networking into teaching and learning processes by creating opportunities for guided discussions, collaborative projects, and the sharing of verified academic content.

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